

SOME ASPECTS OF IDENTIFYING CREDITWORTHINESS IN CORPORATE LOANS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Credit and equivalent operations are allocated to the customer who has a deposit account in the bank, according to his written application (order) on the basis of the contract and in compliance with the general principles of crediting. In some cases (financially stable, positive credit history and constant cash flow to customers, as well as for financing projects included in Government programs), lending through a secondary account opened at a Bank branch can be carried out only with the permission of the Main Bank's Credit Committee. Loans by the bank are repayable (with the obligation to repay the loan), term (for a certain period), solvency (based on the payment of fixed interest payments on the loan received), security (based on the provision of security for the requested loan funds) and purpose (based on the business plan, for a specific purpose) allocated on the basis of conditions.

The organization of bank lending in different countries is based on the regulatory and legal documents of the state. That is, it indicates the need for banks to take into account customer and bank requirements, regulatory documents of the Central Bank, as well as national historical banking affairs.

In our opinion, the deposit base of the commercial banks of our republic is insufficient due to the existence of problems in attracting voluntary savings of the population and business entities to banking institutions.

Lack of long-term resources in banks is the main factor preventing improvement of long-term lending practices of commercial banks. A simple and realistic way to solve this problem is to get a loan from the Central Bank by pledging liquid assets.

But obtaining resources from the Central Bank by commercial banks by pledging liquid assets is not relevant for Russian banking practice. Because the existence of the Stabilization Fund in Russia does not create the need for the Government to increase the volume of public debt by issuing securities.

For banks in developing countries, short-term loans are preferable to long-term investment loans, characterized by high profitability and low risk. The main macroeconomic factor that prevents the development of project financing is the lack of a state investment policy and a policy in the field of updating the

main production funds and strengthening the innovative production potential of the country. The creditworthiness of economic entities is represented by a number of indicators (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Indicators representing the creditworthiness of legal entities¹

- coverage coefficient;
- liquidity coefficient;
- coefficient of provision of funds (autonomy).

Also, the dynamics of availability of working capital, profitability and indicators of turnover of working capital are also of special importance.

Assessment of creditworthiness of economic entities is carried out on the basis of balance sheet and profit and loss reporting. In addition, statistical, analytical and other data are used when necessary during the determination of creditworthiness.

After finding the coefficients determining the client's creditworthiness, he is divided into classes according to the granting of credit. The following table shows the classes of creditworthiness of customers.

Enterprises included in the first class are granted credit on general terms. They can be given blank loans or be offered certain benefits.

Second-class enterprises are also credited on general terms. They are given certain benefits (beyond credit) when certain additional conditions are met. When concluding a contract with such enterprises, additional control measures are agreed upon.

Table 1

¹ Done by the author

Credit eligibility requirements by grade²

No	Indicators	Class 1	Class 2	Class 3
1.	Coverage ratio	$C_r \geq 2,0$	$2,0 \geq C_r \geq 1,0$	$1,0 \geq C_r > 0,5$
2.	Liquidity ratio	$L_r \geq 1,5$	$1,5 > L_r \geq 1,0$	$1,0 \geq L_r > 0,5$
3.	Autonomy ratio	$A_r \geq 60\%$	$60\% > L_r \geq 30\%$	$30\% > L_r > 15\%$

Enterprises included in the third class are considered to have a low level of creditworthiness and can be given credit only on the basis of collateral. Loans are not granted to enterprises rated below the third class.

According to the order of the credit department, a loan account is opened for the company receiving the loan in the accounting and operational department. Depending on the type of business entity, a loan account is opened on the corresponding balance sheet.

The commercial bank should have constant information about the activities of the clients it serves, analyze its creditworthiness, the state of payment discipline, that is, establish a "data bank". In the process of lending, the borrower should focus on fulfilling the terms of the loan agreement, making effective use of the loan, returning it on time and in full, and maintaining close contact with the borrower during the entire period of using the loan. For this purpose, the client's business financial situation, how it fulfills its obligations regarding the delivery of products that do not comply with the concluded contracts, production volumes, wasteful expenses and losses, transaction costs, profit, the dynamics of the increase of its working capital, stocks of goods and materials, and the situation of circulation of working capital is analyzed.

Reconstruction of the lending mechanism of commercial banks in Uzbekistan has become one of the important directions of the economic policy of the independent state. The urgency of introducing scoring methods is the rapid growth of demand for consumer credit in recent years; the credit policy of commercial banks and the increase in cases of non-return of given loans; increase in the loan portfolio of commercial banks; decrease in the level of activity of commercial banks in the field of consumer credit; the level of formation of credit bureaus in the country is at the first stage; high risk level of banks in the consumer and mortgage loan market; explained by the high cost of implementing their own software structure in the analysis of the customer's solvency, etc.

² Done by the author on the basis of economic literatures

The client's ability to receive a loan is the main assessment object in the world banking practice in determining the purposes and forms of their loan in credit relations.

Today, there are several ways to assess a client's creditworthiness, which differ from each other in the amount and method of indicators used as an organizational structure in the overall assessment of clients. But they can be distinguished by the main state of use at the national level (Figure 2).

In conclusion, it can be said that it should be paid attention to valuation risks in corporate loans to eliminate the identified shortcomings and reduce the risks arising in the future in the corporate loans systems.

³ Done by the author

⁴ Done by the author

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